

1 The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape), Integrating Remote 2 Sensing with Biodiversity Science

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17 Abstract

18 There are repeated calls for remote sensing observations to produce accessible data products
19 that improve our understanding and conservation of biodiversity. The Biodiversity Survey of the
20 Cape (BioSCape) addresses this need by integrating field, airborne, satellite, and modeling
21 datasets to advance the limits of global remote sensing of biodiversity. Over six weeks, an
22 international team of ~150 scientists collected data across terrestrial, marine, and freshwater
23 ecosystems in South Africa. *In situ* biodiversity observations of plant and animal communities,
24 estuaries, kelp, and plankton were made using traditional field methods as well as novel
25 approaches like environmental DNA and acoustic surveys. Biodiversity observations were
26 accompanied by an unprecedented combination of airborne imaging spectroscopy and lidar
27 measurements acquired across 45,000km². Here, we review how the approaches applied in
28 BioSCape will help us measure and monitor biodiversity at scale and the role of remote sensing
29 in accomplishing this.

30 Main Text

31 Introduction

32 With over one million species' existence threatened, it is widely recognized that we are in the
33 midst of a sixth mass extinction ¹. Safeguarding biodiversity demands that the "best available
34 data, information and knowledge, are accessible to decision makers, practitioners and the
35 public" ². Creating global biodiversity data products is complex; biogeographic zonation and
36 independent evolutionary histories combined with climatic and environmental variation make
37 biodiversity intrinsically site-specific and one-size-fits-all solutions inappropriate. High-fidelity
38 biodiversity data products require local knowledge and field data, which can be labour intensive
39 and expensive to collect. Recently, technological advancements in survey techniques have

40 increased field data coverage, but spatio-temporal gaps in these measurements persist³. Next-
41 generation remote sensing technology and models can help fill gaps in field data and produce
42 integrated multi-scalar data sets that accelerate biodiversity product generation and improve
43 tracking of progress towards conservation targets⁴⁻⁷. Due to the novelty of such approaches,
44 there is an urgent need to better understand the potential and limitations of integrated field,
45 remote sensing, and modeling datasets for measuring and monitoring biodiversity globally⁸.

46
47 Integrated multi-scalar datasets are useful for uncovering the ecological processes responsible
48 for observed patterns in species abundance and distribution and their change in time and space
49⁹. For example, integrated airborne imaging and field spectroscopy datasets allow the analysis
50 of biodiversity and its relationship to ecosystem function continuously across communities and
51 environmental gradients¹⁰⁻¹³. The addition of three-dimensional structural information to these
52 datasets further enhances their ecological applications¹⁴. Looking forward, integrated datasets
53 will increasingly include measurements from novel field survey approaches, such as
54 autonomous sound recordings and environmental DNA (eDNA), often combined with citizen
55 science observations^{15,16}. Integrated datasets will also more prominently feature next-
56 generation satellite products like light detection and ranging (LiDAR, herein lidar) and other
57 structural data as well as ultraviolet (UV), visible to shortwave infrared (VSWIR), and thermal
58 infrared (TIR) data from imaging spectrometers, as these expand in area covered, spatial
59 resolution, and temporal latency¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

60
61 Quantifying the opportunities and shortcomings of Open Access integrated datasets to conserve
62 biodiversity has never been more important. Addressing this need motivated the US's National
63 Aeronautics and Space Administration's (NASA) first field campaign focused on biodiversity -
64 the Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape) - which took place in South Africa in late 2023.
65 Here, we introduce BioSCape, discuss the motivations for choosing South Africa, and review
66 how the campaign advances remote sensing of biodiversity.

67 The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape

68 BioSCape pairs diverse field measurements made on land and in water with remotely sensed
69 airborne and satellite observations to better understand the structure, function, and composition
70 of ecosystems and how and why they are changing in time and space. BioSCape is organized
71 around three research themes (**FIGURE 1**):

- 72 1) Shifting community composition;
- 73 2) Ecosystem disturbance, resilience, and recovery; and
- 74 3) Ecosystem function and nature's contributions to people.

75
76 Field data were collected by 19 individually funded research projects, each with separate but
77 coordinated objectives (see Expected Contributions). BioSCape's field data set is unique in its
78 diversity and scope - containing novel and traditional field survey measurements in many types
79 of aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems and across multiple environmental gradients. Terrestrial
80 field observations included surveys of more than 600 vegetation plots in protected areas across
81 environmental gradients and additional surveys done in estuarine ecosystems and in
82 landscapes heavily invaded by invasive alien plants. Terrestrial observations also included

83 multi-season sampling of water, soil, and sediment environmental DNA (eDNA) at 36 sites
84 across two watersheds and audio recordings of birds and frogs at more than 500 sites across
85 the region. In the aquatic realm, observations included kelp forest composition and physiological
86 condition at 15 sites as well as biomass, abundance, and taxonomic identification of phyto- and
87 zoo- plankton functional types in four marine bays and four freshwater bodies.

88
89 Contemporaneous airborne data were acquired using six sensors aboard two NASA and one
90 South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) aircraft in October and November
91 2023. UV and VSWIR measurements were collected by the Airborne Visible / Infrared Imaging
92 Spectrometer-Next Generation (AVIRIS-NG) ²⁰ and the Portable Remote Imaging Spectrometer
93 (PRISM) ²¹ integrated onto a NASA Gulfstream III aircraft, while the Hyperspectral Thermal
94 Emission Spectrometer (HyTES) ²² and the Land, Vegetation, and Ice Sensor (LVIS) ²³ were
95 integrated onto a NASA Gulfstream V to collect TIR and full-waveform lidar measurements
96 respectively. At select coastal sites, additional discrete return lidar data (~10 points per metre)
97 were acquired at by an ELMAP-V instrument and high-resolution colour imagery (~13cm pixels)
98 were acquired by a 46MP Nikon D850, both integrated onto the SAEON Airborne Remote
99 Sensing Platform. BioSCape's airborne dataset is unique in its spectral and spatial resolution,
100 covering much of the electromagnetic spectrum at ~2-15 m ground sample distance (**FIGURE**
101 **2**). BioSCape's imaging spectrometers provide data in nearly 1000 well-resolved bands from
102 350 nm (UV) to 12 000 nm (TIR) at a resolution of 3.5 nm in the UV range to 5 nm in the SWIR
103 range and 17.6 nm in the TIR range. The addition of coincident full-waveform large-footprint
104 lidar acquisitions (1064 nm-wavelength laser) as well as discrete return lidar (1030nm laser
105 pulse) complement the optical measurements. Accompanying the airborne measurements are
106 numerous satellite acquisitions, including 240 scenes from EMIT ²⁴, 101 from ECOSTRESS ²⁵,
107 1,051 from Sentinel-2 ²⁶, 168 from Landsat ²⁷, and historical GEDI coverage ²⁸. BioSCape thus
108 represents one of the few combined field, airborne, and orbital spectral and structural datasets
109 available. While the airborne data is collected once off, it will serve as a powerful resource to
110 explore the boundaries of remote sensing for biodiversity measurement across diverse aquatic
111 and terrestrial ecosystems, and through time via links with ongoing satellite acquisitions ²⁹.

112 Why South Africa?

113 BioSCape is focused on the Greater Cape Floristic Region (GCFR) of South Africa. The GCFR
114 is home to astonishing levels of biodiversity, wicked conservation challenges ^{30,31}, and a well-
115 developed and progressive biodiversity research and conservation community ^{32,33}, together
116 providing fertile ground for local impact and global lessons.

117
118 *A megadiverse mesocosm of global challenges* - The GCFR includes the intersections of eight
119 terrestrial and six marine biomes and is known for its extreme topographic and environmental
120 heterogeneity (**FIGURE 3**). It is home to two of the world's richest biodiversity hotspots,
121 containing some 11,500 species of vascular plants, of which 78% are endemic to the region
122 ^{34,35}. The GCFR is also where the cold Benguela and the warm Agulhas Currents meet, leading
123 to regional peaks in marine biodiversity and some of the highest levels of marine endemism
124 globally, with up to a third of about 13,000 marine species being endemic ³⁶⁻³⁸. The GCFR's

125 freshwater aquatic systems also display high amounts of endemism in their fish, frogs, and
126 invertebrate fauna and are listed among the World's 200 Significant Ecoregions ³⁹.

127
128 Like many regions worldwide, the GCFR needs to support human development while
129 conserving its biodiversity in the face of climate change. The region is increasingly drought-
130 prone and the oceans are experiencing rapid warming of offshore ocean currents and upwelling
131 intensification with further increases in ocean temperature, ocean acidity, and storm frequency
132 predicted ⁴⁰⁻⁴². Climate change effects are compounded by significant and somewhat stochastic
133 community reorganization after disturbance by fire or hydrological shocks and by pressure from
134 dense human populations ^{43,44}. As a result, the GCFR has the second highest documented
135 number of vascular plant extinctions in the world, over half of marine and coastal ecosystems
136 are threatened, and nearly half of marine fisheries are over-exploited or collapsed ^{38,45}.

137
138 *A region of challenges and opportunities* - The megadiverse GCFR presents a challenge for
139 remote sensing of biodiversity. On land, the high plant richness is the result of the radiation of a
140 limited number of lineages, which, together with convergent evolution of similar traits among
141 different lineages, has resulted in large numbers of species that are difficult to distinguish ^{46,47}.
142 From a remote sensing perspective, this is aggravated by shrubs being small enough that
143 multiple individuals, and possibly multiple taxonomic groups, are often present in a single pixel.
144 The extreme topography of the region also makes post-processing of remote sensing data
145 difficult and can compromise data quality. In aquatic environments, the optical characteristics
146 and complexity of freshwater and marine environments vary wildly based on nutrient availability
147 and excess. These issues, combined with variations in sediment loads and dissolved organic
148 carbon concentrations that are driven in part by highly localized vegetation and land cover
149 characteristics and land-to-sea biogeochemical transformations, make the applicability of
150 globally-calibrated algorithms challenging for the region ⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰. A lack of aquatic bio-optical
151 datasets in the global south confounds these challenges. In selecting the GCFR, we hope to
152 push the best available technology and theory up to and beyond its current limits, thereby
153 highlighting areas for future research that will result in even broader utility.

154
155 *Local impact and global lessons* - South Africa is a well-known early adopter of systematic
156 conservation planning and has been relatively successful in operationalizing scientific findings
157 into government policy and decision-making ⁵¹. The local scientific community is deeply
158 engaged with research that speaks to the information needs of stakeholders, and BioSCape has
159 strongly emphasized incorporating local knowledge from its inception ^{33,52}. We expect that
160 BioSCape's data products will feed into the GCFR's established pathways from science to
161 application. In doing so, we hope that BioSCape can help set an example of science diplomacy
162 and research for good.

163 Expected Contributions

164 All BioSCape data products will be Open Access, and will be accessible through a cloud
165 computing environment throughout the analytical stage of the project. In addition to the regularly
166 delivered Level 1 and 2 airborne data products, BioSCape is also producing Level 3
167 orthomosaics of surface reflectance from AVIRIS-NG and PRISM, relative heights from LVIS,

168 and possibly surface temperature and emissivity from HyTES. These orthomosaics will be co-
169 registered to a common grid with a common spatial resolution (5x5 m, with select regions at
170 2x2m). This level of data harmonization is unprecedented for an Open Access multi-sensor
171 airborne campaign and we hope will set a new standard for data accessibility⁵³. BioSCape's
172 data analysis workflows, including airborne data harmonization, will also largely be open source
173 and made available with publications and/or on public GitHub repositories versioned with a DOI,
174 and all data will be made available through the Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Data
175 Archiving Centre¹⁰⁵. This will increase interoperability of data products and the reproducibility of
176 the science. In this section, we summarize how the campaign is using data optimized for
177 usability to test the limits and potential of remote sensing for global biodiversity applications.

178
179 The spatial resolution of BioSCape pixels, while finer than any spaceborne spectroscopic
180 measurements to date, are typically coarser than the individual organisms being studied and
181 result in pixels with mixed spectral signatures. While one can often identify the endmembers
182 (species or cover types) contributing to the mixed signal using spectral unmixing (e.g.⁵⁴,
183 another approach is to look at the diversity of spectral signatures across a window of pixels.
184 Spectral diversity has been shown to predict functional and phylogenetic diversity as well as
185 ecosystem function, although there are limitations to this approach⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷. Methods like Intrinsic
186 Dimensionality (ID), that allow us to estimate spectral diversity without training data, are some of
187 the few viable approaches to map biodiversity at a global scale using comparable metrics
188 across geographic regions⁵⁸⁻⁶¹. Measures of spectral beta diversity can be combined with
189 statistical techniques such as Generalized Dissimilarity Modeling or Spatial Generalized
190 Dissimilarity Mixed Modeling to explore drivers of spectral turnover or to estimate spectral
191 gamma diversity^{62,63}. ID has been used to estimate diversity in marine phytoplankton
192 communities and tropical forest and desert landscapes, but it has never been extensively
193 calibrated with field observations, with multiple sensors, and across environmental or diversity
194 gradients^{60,64}. BioSCape represents the largest application of ID to field data and will help us
195 delineate what this promising method can do for remote sensing of biodiversity at the global
196 scale.

197
198 Spectral signatures are inherently a combination of the underlying structure and chemistry of the
199 system; put another way, functional traits define the spectroscopy of plants. Pixels with similar
200 spectral signatures, so called "spectral species"^{65,66}, and their associated functional traits can
201 be mapped across a landscape⁶⁷. In land plants, certain functional traits can be mapped using
202 empirical relationships derived between field-measured trait values and associated airborne
203 spectral reflectance values^{68,69}. This approach works for single sites and can work for regions,
204 but it struggles to scale further since the calibration relationships can be site-, and sensor-, or
205 date- specific⁶⁸. The challenge of parameterizing spectra-trait relationships that are applicable
206 globally is further exacerbated by the geographic bias in imaging spectroscopy data acquisition.
207 To date, very little imaging spectroscopy has been acquired on the African continent. BioSCape
208 provides a unique opportunity to test the potential impact of this geographic bias and will
209 compare similar ecosystems across continents and assess both the difference in calibration
210 equations and the accuracy of these equations to map functional traits from remotely sensed
211 imagery⁷⁰. The BioSCape AVIRIS-NG acquisitions, the first from this sensor on the African

212 continent, are well placed to be compared to the extensive acquisitions along the West Coast of
213 the United States - which has, in parts, a similar climate and vegetation biome to the GCFR.
214 Once functional traits have been mapped, they can be clustered and examined with
215 environmental variables and structural data to better understand the drivers of biodiversity and
216 inform conservation decisions ⁷¹.

217
218 Leaf spectra have been demonstrated to correlate with plant phylogenetic history ⁷².
219 Phylogenetic diversity does not perfectly align with functional diversity due to trait convergence,
220 which causes different lineages living in similar environments to develop similar functional traits.
221 When evaluated with spectral and functional diversity, phylogenetic diversity can provide deep
222 insight into the drivers of functional trait variation across abiotic gradients and spatial scales ⁷³.
223 The links between spectral, functional, and phylogenetic diversity have been explored for the
224 BioSCape study region using leaf-level data ⁵⁵ but can now be tested using airborne and
225 satellite remote sensing data. The astonishing levels of taxonomic diversity and yet surprisingly
226 low variation in physiognomy in this biodiversity hotspot will test the limits of these methods ⁴⁷.

227
228 In aquatic environments, remote sensing of biodiversity is challenging as vegetation and
229 phytoplankton are often partially or entirely submerged in water, interfering with their spectral
230 signature. In coastal and inland waters, high concentrations of suspended sediments or
231 coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) also make it difficult to detect and discriminate
232 between different plant and phytoplankton functional types ^{74,75}. Adding to this challenge, the
233 water leaving signal is a very small component of the overall signal received by the sensor
234 (usually less than 10%) ⁷⁶. To resolve phytoplankton and plant functional types, a sensor must
235 have a high signal-to-noise ratio to detect small changes to water-leaving radiances and
236 distinguish these from the water and atmospheric radiance measurements. Additionally, the
237 sensor needs to capture high spatial resolution data, since freshwater floating plants and marine
238 kelp may be limited in their extent, and data must be collected with relatively low solar zenith
239 angles to avoid sunglint from impeding the signal ⁷⁷⁻⁷⁹. BioSCape's data over coastal and inland
240 waters has a high spatial (~1 - 15 m) and spectral resolution and excellent signal-to-noise ratios,
241 with PRISM having a ratio of 500 or more to one at 450 nm. By coupling PRISM and AVIRIS-
242 NG on the same platform, BioSCape made simultaneous spectral measurements across the UV
243 to the SWIR, which may enable improvements in corrections for sunglint and aerosols to
244 enhance remote sensing detection of aquatic biodiversity. When coupled with the near-
245 simultaneous acquisition of thermal imaging spectroscopy from HyTES, this is the first time that
246 such detailed radiance measurements have been collected by multiple spectrometers
247 concurrently with field measurements at the confluence of major oceanic currents and over
248 freshwater bodies.

249
250 Detecting change in biodiversity is difficult, as any departure from expected radiance or
251 reflectance values needs to be attributable to a change in community composition or ecosystem
252 function rather than a background change in the atmosphere or water column values. One can
253 use first-principle physical laws to address this attribution challenge by using radiative transfer
254 models (RTMs) to generate synthetic background or baseline measurements of a system ^{80,81}.
255 RTMs' synthetic measurements can be compared to measured radiance and reflectance values

256 to help disentangle disturbance signals from background noise. RTMs are especially useful for
257 remote sensing of phytoplankton communities, where differentiating signals from the water
258 column and the target communities is difficult ⁸². RTMs are also useful in terrestrial plant
259 communities where there is high natural variability through space and time and thus departures
260 from the “natural” state of the ecosystem can be hard to detect unless one has a suitable model
261 of the expected signal of a “natural” state ^{83,84}. In inland and coastal waters, BioSCape’s
262 innovative combination of sensors will facilitate development and testing of new machine
263 learning algorithms, making an essential contribution to water quality measurement and
264 monitoring ⁸⁵. On land, BioSCape will use 3D RTMs to develop synthetic reflectance datasets
265 for several different vegetation types that will be compared to terrestrial and airborne lidar and
266 airborne imaging spectroscopy datasets ⁸⁶. These next-generation RTMs can assist in detecting
267 alien plant invasions and abnormal post-fire vegetation recovery trajectories, as well as provide
268 baseline datasets for various functional and structural trait measurements.

269
270 In the GCFR and other Mediterranean ecosystems, one of the most widespread changes in
271 community composition and threats to biodiversity is the increase in the abundance of invasive
272 alien plants ⁸⁷. Invasive alien plants decrease biodiversity by replacing indigenous plant species
273 and disrupt the normal fire regime by altering fuel loads and fire severity and frequency ^{88,89}.
274 Invasive alien trees in the region also alter ecosystem function by dramatically increasing water
275 use and evapotranspiration while decreasing runoff and groundwater recharge ^{90–92}.
276 Groundwater-dependent ecosystems provide many contributions to people, including ensuring
277 water quality, and their sensitivity to invasive alien trees and groundwater abstraction is largely
278 unknown as the linkages between surface and groundwater are highly complex ⁹³. BioSCape
279 will combine spectral information with structural information to quantify and map alien invasive
280 trees, flammable fuel loads, and water use efficiency across various invaded landscapes as well
281 as groundwater dependent ecosystems in the region.

282
283 Changes in aquatic community composition can affect ecosystem function and services. For
284 example, phytoplankton functional type and abundance are key determinants of water quality,
285 kelp forests support healthy fish populations, remove nitrogen from the water column and may
286 act as blue carbon stores, while estuaries play a role in coastal protection and maintenance of
287 fisheries ^{94–96}. BioSCape will develop and apply algorithms for airborne spectroscopy to map
288 phytoplankton functional types based on their accessory pigments and to map kelp forest extent
289 and physiological condition. By developing these algorithms for multiple marine and, where
290 relevant, inland water bodies across anthropogenic and environmental gradients, BioSCape will
291 contribute towards harmful algal bloom and kelp forest monitoring efforts. Additionally,
292 BioSCape will map estuarine biodiversity variables to make predictions about how these
293 systems’ contributions to people may change with changes in climate, especially sea level rise.
294 All of these research objectives will have global applicability, but are especially important to
295 address in water scarce regions with little redundancy in drinking water supply and in places
296 with economically important fishing and aqua- and agri- culture industries, as is the case in the
297 GCFR ^{97,98}.

298

299 Understanding the complex links between biodiversity, ecosystem function, and nature's
300 contribution to people requires not only different types of remote sensing data but also an
301 abundance of high-quality field measurements. Technological advancements in field methods
302 have changed the type and increased the amount of low-cost high-coverage biodiversity
303 information we can collect. The novelty of these field biodiversity measurements means they
304 have not yet been reliably related to remotely sensing biodiversity information. For example,
305 multi-locus metabarcoding of environmental DNA (eDNA) from soils, sediment, and water can
306 extend species identification to microorganisms and non-vascular plants, in addition to the
307 vascular plants and vertebrates captured in traditional field surveys^{5,15}. These molecular
308 methods can facilitate new insights into the organization of ecological communities - for
309 instance, eDNA samples collected in rivers can provide an integrated field-based measure of
310 biodiversity across the entire watershed and can be better than traditional surveys at detecting
311 small, rare, or otherwise cryptic species^{99,100}. Genetic composition is the only Essential
312 Biodiversity Variable class "not yet measurable from space"⁷. To address this gap, BioSCape
313 will correlate ground-based eDNA estimates of allelic diversity with remotely sensed diversity
314 metrics across multiple watersheds and along a gradient of human influence. Such an approach
315 has been successfully trialed in California⁵, and BioSCape hopes to advance this field
316 significantly. Like eDNA, autonomous recording units deployed across a landscape allow us to
317 gather biodiversity information about birds, frogs, and other potential indicator species over
318 large areas quickly and at relatively low cost^{16,101-104}. BioSCape will aim to link acoustic diversity
319 with plant and structural diversity determined from airborne spectroscopy and lidar data. Both
320 eDNA and acoustic diversity provide novel biodiversity information that, when paired with
321 remote sensing data, has great potential to improve the accuracy of biodiversity measurement
322 at regional to global scales.

323 Conclusion

324 Addressing biodiversity loss is a global priority and there is a clear need to improve our ability to
325 map and monitor change. Due to its complexity, the GCFR represents one of the most
326 challenging environments for remote sensing of biodiversity, but also presents myriad
327 opportunities. BioSCape's findings will advance our understanding of biodiversity in South Africa
328 and have far-reaching implications for global biodiversity science, inclusive international
329 research projects, data-driven conservation, and effective ecosystem management. All
330 BioSCape data are Open Access and will be made available through the Oak Ridge National
331 Laboratory Distributed Data Archiving Centre¹⁰⁵. The project's innovative methods and insights
332 will help define the potential and the limits of biodiversity measurement and monitoring using
333 remote sensing. In doing so, we hope BioSCape can guide the development of appropriate
334 biodiversity proxies that can be observed from space, ultimately contributing to preserving our
335 planet's rich biodiversity.

337
 338 **FIGURE 1:** BioSCape is an integrated airborne remote sensing and field campaign. Airborne data were
 339 acquired contemporaneously with a variety of field measurements of biodiversity. These data are processed
 340 through models and algorithms to produce products that inform our understanding of functional, taxonomic,
 341 phylogenetic, and spectral dimensions of biodiversity. Applying these biodiversity data products will help
 342 inform the measuring and management of biodiversity resources and nature’s contribution to people
 343 (Artwork created by J.Silver under contract with BioSCape).

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 352 **FIGURE 2:** BioSCape airborne data were acquired using three imaging spectrometers: AVIRIS-NG,
 353 PRISM, and HyTES. This figure summarizes the key spectral characteristics of the instruments and
 354 compares them with commonly used instruments with free and open access data policies, and anticipated
 355 future missions. a) Data were collected across the electromagnetic spectrum, from 350 nm (UV) to 2500
 356 nm (SWIR) using AVIRIS-NG and PRISM and b) from 7500 nm to 12 000 nm (TIR) using HyTES, at a
 357 resolution of 3.5 nm in the UV range to 5 nm in the SWIR range and 17 nm in the TIR range. c) Full
 358 waveform airborne lidar data were also acquired using the LVIS instrument. LVIS measures the full
 359 distribution of returned laser pulses to the active sensor, capturing more information about topography and
 360 vegetation structure than standard discrete return airborne lidar sensors, which typically capture 1-4
 361 discrete points from a single laser pulse. (Artwork in 2c created by A. Ibrahim and J.Flora under contract
 362 with BioSCape)

363
 364

365
 366 **FIGURE 3:** a) Terrestrial biomes and marine bioregions of the BioSCape study area (the Greater Cape
 367 Floristic Region) in the South-Western corner of South Africa and b-d) Airborne data coverage by four of
 368 the airborne instruments over the study area. (3b-d are screengrabs from the BioSCape Data Portal,
 369 popo.jpl.nasa.gov/mmgis-aviris/?mission=BIOSCAPE).

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405 Competing Interests

406 The authors have no competing interests.

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